

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D4.5

Scientific Aims, Testable Hypotheses
and Scientifically Sound, Evidence-
based Recommendations for the
Assessment and Management of
CoBraD in real-world practice – v4

September 2023

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PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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Table of Contents

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	8
1 INTRODUCTION	10
2 Work Group Aims, Hypotheses, Methods, Outcomes, & Recommendations.....	12
2.1 Complex Brain Disorders work groups.....	12
2.1.1 Sleep and Wearables Work Group (WG- SW).....	12
2.1.2 Neurodegeneration and Neuropsychological Testing Work Group (WG-ND/NPS)	15
2.1.3 Epilepsy Work Group (WG-Epilepsy).....	18
2.2 Real World Data work groups.....	19
2.2.1 Magnetic Resonance Imaging Work Group (WG-MRI).....	19
2.2.2 Biofluids Work Group (WG-BF)	21
2.3 Science of Science work groups	22
2.3.1 Machine Learning and Expert Systems Work Group (WG-ML).....	22
2.3.2 Automatic Quality Control Work Group (WG-autoQC)	23
2.3.3 User Interface Work Group (WG-UX)	24
2.4 Socioeconomic work groups.....	26
2.4.1 Ethics, Policy, Society work group (WG-Policy).....	26
3 Publication & Presentation References	28

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Sleep and wearables work group information	12
Table 2 Neurodegeneration and neurophysiological testing work group information	15
Table 3 Epilepsy work group information.....	18
Table 4 Magnetic resonance imaging work group information	19
Table 5 Biofluids work group information	21
Table 6 Machine learning and expert systems work group information.....	22
Table 7 Automatic quality control work group information.....	23
Table 8 User interface work group information.....	24
Table 9 Ethics, policy, society work group information	26
Table 10 Publication and presentation references information	28

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AD-GC	Alzheimer's Disease Genetics Consortium
ADNI	Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative
AHI	Apnoea Hypopnea Index
AI	Artificial intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
APOe	Apolipoprotein E
ASL	Arterial spin labelling
CAI	Central apnea index
CBS	Cognitive and Behavioural Symptoms
cCBS	Carer Cognitive and Behavioural Symptoms
CERAD	Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease
CFI	Circadian Function Index
CoBraD	Complex Brain Disorders
CPAP	Continuous positive airway pressure
CSA	Central sleep apnea
DWI	Diffusion-Weighted Imaging
EEG	Electroencephalography
ELISA	Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay
ES	Expert System
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FLAIR	Fluid-attenuated inversion recovery
GFAP	Glial fibrillary acidic protein
HC	Healthy Controls
ICD-11	International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision
IEDs	Interictal Epileptiform Discharges
LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MVR	Mean Variance Regularization
Mx	Month x
ND	Neurodegeneration
NfL	Neurofilament Light Chain
NIV	Non-invasive ventilation
No.	Number
NPS	Neuropsychology
NPT	Neuropsychological Testing
OSA	Obstructive Sleep Apnea
PCA	Principal component analysis
PEA	Proximity Extension Assay

pTAU	phosphorylated-Tau
PSPS	Progressive Supranuclear Palsy Syndrome
PUC	Pilot Use Case
QC	Quality Control
RBD	Rapid eye movement (REM) sleep behavior disorder
ROI	Region of interest
rsfMRI	Resting state functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
RWD	Real World Data
SAMSEG	Sequence Adaptive Multimodal SEGmentation
SDH	Social Determinants of Health
SE	Sleep Efficiency
SES	Socioeconomic Status
Simoa	Single-molecule array
SOL	sleep onset latency
SpO2	Saturation of Peripheral Oxygen
SVM	support vector machine
TMT	Trail Making Test
ToC	Table of Contents
UX	User Interface
VLT	Verbal Learning Test
WASO	Wakefulness After Sleep Onset
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 INTRODUCTION

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with CoBraD, as represented in Neurocognitive (e.g., Alzheimer's dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (i.e., Epilepsy) disorders. The principles followed within the MES-CoBraD Project can be generalized for the assessment and management of other Chronic Complex Conditions (CCC) by exploiting advanced analytics modules and RWD acquisition protocols.

Work Package 4 (WP4) defines the methodological process for the analysis of the RWD acquired during pilot data acquisition (WP8) to address the challenges faced in CoBraD and share the results within the Consortium and through scientific publications prior to wider dissemination (WP9). It is one of three WPs (WP4, WP6, WP8) serving scientific objectives whose tasks were distributed for operational efficiency and minimization of errors.

The main objectives of WP4 are:

- › Achieve scientific and social objectives, promote scientific productivity, and solve unforeseen problems
- › Oversee that principles of scientific methods are followed in pursued analyses
- › Perform scientific analyses and disseminate knowledge equitably and according to ethical principles
- › Identify significant results and maximize their impact through multidisciplinary expert contributions
- › Integrate MES-CoBraD Platform Database and Advanced Analytics Modules in maximizing scientific impact

To achieve these goals, nine Work Groups (WG)¹ are active as of the current deliverable (unchanged from the previous version D4.3), and organized into four main categories: Complex Brain Disorders, Real World Data, Science of Science, and Socioeconomic work groups. The full list is:

- › Complex Brain Disorders work groups
 - Sleep and Wearables Work Group (WG-SW)
 - Neurodegeneration and Neuropsychological Testing Work Group (WG-ND/NPS)
 - Epilepsy Work Group (WG-Epilepsy)
- › Real World Data work groups
 - Magnetic Resonance Imaging Work Group (WG-MRI)
 - Biofluids Work Group (WG-BF)
- › Science of Science work groups
 - Machine Learning and Expert Systems Work Group (WG-ML)
 - Automatic Quality Control Work Group (WG-autoQC)

¹ WG-MRI is currently led by RMC after the departure of the respective expert from SP

- User Interface Work Group (WG-UX)
- › Socioeconomic work groups
 - Ethics, Policy, Society Work Group (WG-Policy)

Since D4.4, we have restructured our WG meetings to be incorporated into the Scientific meetings to increase participation and coordinate across scientific and technical partners in improving technological innovations of the MES-CoBraD Platform. The meetings still discuss the scientific landscape of the respective WG field of expertise and propose research hypotheses and relevant methodologies for their testing, aiming to proceed to its hypothesis testing through a structured collaborative process, and minutes are recorded and stored in our shared secure platform. Considering the rapid pace of scientific advancement, the relevance, feasibility, and plausibility of hypotheses and their analyses are re-evaluated, modified, updated, or even cancelled, and new ones have been considered, depending on current clinical, social, and scientific evidence. The hypotheses throughout the project are re-assessed according to the latest scientific literature, acquired RWD, analysis results and the advancement of technological deliverables.

In this deliverable, we include updates over the six months since D4.4 delivery. Furthermore, D4.5 includes references to all submitted scientific publications, resulting in scientifically sound, evidence-based recommendations informing professional organizations, policy, healthcare, and insurance stakeholders on changes that can improve assessment and management of CoBraD in real-world practice. The final installation of these deliverables, D4.6 will present the final outcome of WP4, providing a summary of all scientific publications that resulted from the project, including the final Guidelines for Professional Diagnostic Practice or Safety and Efficacy of Real-World Medical Therapies.

At the time of D4.5 delivery, anticipating across-site data harmonization and secure integration and advanced analytics module availability on the first installation of the MES-CoBraD platform, there are no multi-site data analysed through the WG. This is in keeping with the no-cost extension granted to the project for six months to complete its stated goals. That said, MES-CoBraD researchers have shared with the wider scientific community outcomes from their work on CoBraD as individual partners (within-site publications and presentations) if that work followed from the objectives and goals of MES-CoBraD proposal and was realized through MES-CoBraD funding. As required, all these publications or presentations reference funding being related to the MES-CoBraD Project. In addition to being tabulated in tables below, they are referenced through WP9 deliverables.

Updates from D4.4:

No new hypotheses have been proposed, and none rejected. A few more leaders were identified per hypothesis. Three abstracts were presented at the AAIC 2023 in Amsterdam, 35th International Epilepsy Congress in Dublin and 9th Congress of the European Academy of Neurology in Budapest. Three new publications were made in Alzheimer's & Dementia as well as Translational Neurodegeneration. Several manuscripts have been submitted and are under revision as well (not mentioned in tables).

These updates are based on internal documents and tables that WG leaders are tasked to update. The following reflects these updates. Overall, hypotheses remain the same to the last report. Collaborative testing is pending on the first integration of modular components of the MES-CoBraD Platform.

2 WORK GROUP AIMS, HYPOTHESES, METHODS, OUTCOMES, & RECOMMENDATIONS

2.1 COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS WORK GROUPS

2.1.1 SLEEP AND WEARABLES WORK GROUP (WG- SW)

Table 1 Sleep and wearables work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Worse OSA (AHI, SpO ₂ , %time <92%) associated with higher NfL, lower amyloid-β and higher phospho-tau	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
	Worse CSA (CAI) associated with higher phospho-tau		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
	Worse OSA (AHI, SpO ₂ , %time <92%) associated with more MRI atrophy		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Relationship between sleep apnea and cognitive function	Self reported OSA (STOP-Bang) associated with worse cognition as reflected in MMSE, TMT, digits BW FW, learning curve in VLT/CERAD, rapid naming	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Relationship between sleep continuity and regularity and neurodegenerative biomarkers	More sleep fragmentation (#arousals, WASO, SE) actigraphy (intradaily variability and interdaily stability, relative amplitude – > CFI; other markers?) will be associated with worse biosample levels (phospho-tau, amyloid, NfL)	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity; 3. function for calculating CFI or other metrics; 4. Circulized addition models;	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

Relationship between sleep apnea and cognitive function	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better cognitive outcomes (executive: trails, digits BW FW; memory and learning: VLT/CERAD; language: rapid naming)	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity; 3. function for calculating CFI or other metrics; 4. Circulized addition models;	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results; anticipation of few patient data on PAP/NIV to allow for definitive answers	N/A	No
Relationship between sleep apnea treatment and sleep quality/quantity	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better sleep metrics (sleep diary TST, SOL, SE) and actigraphy (interdaily variability and stability, relative amplitude)	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity; 3. function for calculating CFI or other metrics; 4. Circulized addition models;	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results; anticipation of few patient data on PAP/NIV to allow for definitive answers	N/A	No
Relationship between sleep apnea treatment and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better sleep metrics (sleep diary TST, SOL, SE) and biological markers (NfL, phospho-tau, amyloid)	1. correlation coefficient; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity; 3. function for calculating CFI or other metrics; 4. Circulized addition models;	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results anticipation of few patient data on PAP/NIV to allow for definitive answers	N/A	No
	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better imaging markers (MRI volumes, ASL, microcortical structure, vascular burden FLAIR)		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results anticipation of few patient data on PAP/NIV to allow for definitive answers	N/A	No
Relationship between sleep apnea and longitudinal neurodegenerative biomarker metrics	For all cross-sectional hypotheses, baseline status will be predictive of follow up outcomes in respective categories	1. account for temporal interval as covariate/cofactor	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Identify prevalence of sleep and circadian rhythm disorders across neurodegenerative and other dementias	Anticipate that each group of dementias will have at least 50-80% chance of having at least one sleep/circadian disorder	1. prevalence of diagnosis/feature x compared to diagnosis/feature y	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No

	People with a specific neurodegenerative condition will have unique sleep and circadian phenotypes (insomnia in PSPS, RBD in Synucleinopathies)		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Establish normative data for actigraphy	Younger people will not have difference in interdaily variability than non-impaired older people who do not have abnormal neurodegenerative markers	1. prevalence of diagnosis/feature x compared to diagnosis/feature y	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Relationship between dynamic features of cognition and sleep architecture	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be dependent on specific sleep architecture metrics, and varied by type of cognitive domain (TST for executive and memory; N3 sleep for episodic memory, REM sleep for executive function, cycle integrity with both executive and memory)	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function. Sleep architecture: % of TST as N1, N2, N3, REM; Cycles #, WASO, TST	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
	Sleep-mediated cognitive testing will be more sensitive than within day cognitive performance (MMSE, VLT, fluency) on sleep architecture metrics (TST for executive and memory; N3 sleep for episodic memory, REM sleep for executive function, cycle integrity with both executive and memory)	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function.	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Relationship between dynamic features of cognition and sleep disordered breathing	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be dependent on specific sleep disordered breathing metrics, and varied by type of cognitive domain (amount of SpO2 time < 92% but not AHI related to executive function; CSA index related to executive function more than memory function) AHI, spo2 compared to (executive - Fluency, Match), (episodic memory - Favorites,	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function.	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

Appointment)

Sleep-mediated cognitive testing will be more sensitive than within day cognitive performance (MMSE, VLT, fluency) on sleep apnea metrics

Valid

Pending data integration;
Pending results

N/A

Yes

*Rows in bold have a leader actively directing hypothesis testing

2.1.2 NEURODEGENERATION AND NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL TESTING WORK GROUP (WG-ND/NPS)

Table 2 Neurodegeneration and neurophysiological testing work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Updated aim: To develop new tools for quantifying neurodegenerative clinical severity and longitudinal outcomes	Brief tools to ascertain CDR severity will provide comparable outcomes to an entire CDR interview	Updated methods: develop a model using decision tree, xgboost, and validate it (2 groups), sustain Input variables of MoCa and FAQ in predicting CDR	Valid/updated	Pending data integration; within partner preliminary results indicate: training model on data external to COBRAD - NACC shows high ROC~ 89% for each CDR subdomain.	Pending final analyses	Yes
Updated aim: To develop new tools for quantifying neurodegenerative clinical severity and longitudinal outcomes	Longitudinal model accuracy will remain high, and trajectory changes will be smaller within than between participants	Updated methods: develop a model using decision tree, xgboost, and validate it (2 groups), sustain Input variables of MoCa and FAQ in predicting CDR Pending longitudinal analyses	valid	Pending data collection	N/A	Yes

Updated aim: To develop new tools for quantifying neurodegenerative clinical severity and longitudinal outcomes	adding data regarding non memory symptoms (language, mood, behaviour) helps stage atypical dementias , such as FTD	Updated methods: develop a model using decision tree, xgboost, and validate it (2 groups), sustain Input variables of MoCa and FAQ in predicting CDR. And also Language mood and behavior	Valid	Pending data collection	N/A	Yes
Updated aim: To develop new tools for quantifying neurodegenerative clinical severity and longitudinal outcomes	Neurocognitive symptom inventory can adequately separate amnesic from atypical neurodegenerative cognitive decline (language, behavior, motor, mood/personality, visuospatial)	dimensionality reduction, decision tree, logistic and linear multivariate regression, spearman, mann-whitney, wilcoxon, kruskal wallis	Valid	Pending data collection	N/A	Yes
Assessing utility of self-administered symptom checklist	Tailored self-assessment checklists (CBS/cCBS and NCI) will provide comparable outcomes to gold standard clinician structured interviews for gross symptoms	Correlation on neuropsych+physical+consensus to self reported forms Updated methods: reliance on third person input on person's status CBS/cCBS and NCI inventories	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Update: Historical Symptom screen and cognitive testing can predict brain atrophy pattern	Brain atrophy in specific areas will be best related to self-reported symptoms of visuospatial and memory complaints, and less so language and executive complaints. Similarly to cognitive testing	Correlation between checklist leading sympom to ROI cortical thickness Updated methods: dimensionality reduction, decision tree, logistic and linear multivariate regression, spearman, mann-whitney, wilcoxon, kruskal wallis Correlation of cognitive tests to ROI volumes	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Updated: Cognitive symptoms as markers of cognitive reserve	The appearance of symptoms themselves can inform cognitive reserve theory	Updated methods: dimensionality reduction, decision tree, logistic and linear multivariate regression, spearman, mann-whitney, wilcoxon, kruskal wallis	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

D4.5

Scientific Aims, Testable Hypotheses and Scientifically Sound, Evidence-based Recommendations for the Assessment and Management of CoBraD in real-world practice – v4

Assess Social Determinants of Health (SDH) and their impact on ND severity and RWD variability	Adverse social health determinants (predictor) linked to poor scores on cognitive testing, more severe atrophy and white matter hyperintensities, faster progression of decline (outcome)	PCA, logistic regression, L2-regularized algorithms Updated methods: (education, neighborhood disparity, health utilization, others) associations to (sleep,,seizure metrics) and progressive (dementia) cognitive scores	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
New: Assess Social Determinants of Health (SDH) and their impact on ND severity and RWD variability	In people with the same CDR score, SDH will cause variability in basic and advanced cognitive tests ranging up to 0.5 SD	Updated methods: (education, neighborhood disparity, health utilization, others) associations to (sleep,,seizure metrics) and progressive (dementia) cognitive scores	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Assess neurodegenerative structural brain changes in older adults with new onset seizures or sleep disorders (moved from, WG-MRI)	AD signature similarity (%) will be higher in such individuals than without COBRAD	logistic regression, CTh measure. Signature neurodegeneration (Dickerson etal 2009)	Valid / Hypothesis more appropriate for WG-MRI			No
Establish neuropsych normative data	Neuropsych scores are more accurate to clinician diagnosis, CDR/FAQ/ECOG or neuropsych signature when correcting for education, neighborhood disadvantage index and bilingualism / language of test administration	Descriptive statistics, AN(C)OVA, LDA/SVM	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Improve diagnosis for comorbid CoBraD	multimodal data can help assess risk for co-morbid mis- or under- diagnosed CoBraD	use of imaging/genetic/clinical risk scores to predict incidence of late life COBRAD use external database with healthy subjects (ADNI, AD-GC), to compare to subjects in MES-CoBraD	Valid/Integrated under WG-MRI			No
Validation of prior studies in MES-CoBraD cohort	Outcomes from large studies on CoBraD are more likely to be cross-validated in the MES-CoBraD sample than smaller studies	Implementation of prior study analyses. Assess phenotype outcome congruency	Valid / Multiple WG hypotheses / non specific	Distribution across other hypotheses		No

Assess accuracy of predicting specific CoBraD from individual RWD	imaging will best predict specific ND, EEG/PSG Epilepsy, PSG and questionnaires sleep disorders. Longitudinal data will be more accurate than cross sectional data	External cross validation on subset of variables from within individual RWD that for a specific CoBraD. LDA/SVM, correlation, ANOVA.	Valid / Better assessed under WG-MRI	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
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2.1.3 EPILEPSY WORK GROUP (WG-EPILEPSY)

Table 3 Epilepsy work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Explore EEG background activities with results of Neuropsychology assessment	EEG slowing will correlate to worse Neuropsychology/Neurocognition	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG to confirm level of slowing. Correlation statistics	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore EEG background activities in relation to brain MRI	EEG slowing related to worse dorsal and medial temporal MRI atrophy. Asymmetry in slow waves and related to lateralized MRI atrophy	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG to confirm level of slowing. Correlation statistics	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
Explore EEG epileptic activities with Neuropsychology	Amount of (by definition) IEDs are related to worse Neuropsychology scores	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Localisation/number related to NeuroPsychology	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore EEG epileptic activities with Neuropsychology and cognition	Topography of IEDs (by definition IEDs) will be related to specific types of cognitive decline relating to brain network involved	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Localisation/number related to NeuroPsychology scores	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore EEG background with risk for seizures	Quantitative EEG analysis modules will help predict risk for seizures with fair accuracy	Quantitative analysis tools such as FFT compared to visually inspected seizure activity	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

Explore EEG ictal or epileptiform activities in relation to medications	Quantitative and qualitative EEG analysis will be modulated according to drug timing / seizure onset	Quantitative analysis tools such as FFT	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
Explore relation of stress, EEG and seizures	EEG epileptiform features (background frequencies, Epileptiform discharges) will be related to higher stress markers (hair and blood cortisol). These effects will be mediated by AED and Epilepsy phenotypes	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Localisation/number related to NeuroPsychology, Perceived stress scale, Life adverse events and hair and blood cortisol level	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore relation of stress with Complex Brain Disorders	Hair cortisol levels will differentially relate to Epilepsy, sleep and dementia. With higher correlation to epilepsy, early dementia, and insomnia, and less correlation to advanced dementia and RBD	Cortisol ANOVA to different types/subtypes of disorders	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore possible relation of EEG with current medication	EEG background frequencies correlates with type/doses of specific antiepileptic drugs	Quantitative EEG analysis and antiepileptic drugs correlation	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Explore EEG with biomarkers of Complex Brain Disorders	Biological markers indicative of worse neurodegeneration in dementia patients will correlate more with subclinical EDs runs (amount of EDs in patients without overt seizures)	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Localisation/number related to NeuroPsychology scores	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
Explore actigraphy data to EEG and clinical onset of seizures	Actigraphy changes will be stereotyped and different before onset of specific types of seizures (GTC vs. absence)	Actigraphy data analyzed in conjunction with EEG ictal data and time of clinical seizure onset. Correlation analyses	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

2.2 REAL WORLD DATA WORK GROUPS

2.2.1 MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING WORK GROUP (WG-MRI)

Table 4 Magnetic resonance imaging work group information

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Quantify (and correct) T1w acquisition difference over Region of Interest (ROI) volume in CoBraD	We will find site differences. Such differences can be corrected with harmonization methods (e.g Combat)	Compute ROI volumes from MRI scans (obtained with SAMSEG). Evaluate harmonization methods by group-wise comparisons	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Test between defacing algorithms	Newer versions will overcome hacking-strategies of re-identifying participants	several packages implementations	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Automatic Quality Control (QC) of MRI	QC measures will help to separate non-informative MRI from informative ones.	MRI QC	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Define normative data within CoBraD phenotypes	Overlapping metrics will exist between CoBraD phenotypes, especially when comorbid CoBraD are present.	Compute z-score for individual participants compared to same CoBraD group and versus Healthy controls. Individual reports based on normalized data (w-score / z-score)	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Predict (clinical/NPS/biomarkers) missing info	SVM models trained with MRI-driven RWD, will allow to predict specific missing data, especially, those markers related to neurodegeneration and cognitive decline	Define training and test samples. Hyperparameter fitting with backprop. Check accuracy (i.e similarity)	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Prediction of future outcomes in epilepsy/stroke patients (based on rsfMRI or DWI connectome)	The combination of (1) identification of hot-spots and (2) using spreading models based on connectomics will improve the prediction of clinical evolution/recovery of the participants with epilepsy or stroke	Prepare a connectome-matrix with ROI-ROI connections. Implement a diffusion propagation algorithm. Implement prediction scores	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
CoBraD differences in brain structure alterations	We will identify a structural pattern that allows to differentiate between the different CoBraD, accounting by co-occurrence of disease. We will also identify a set of cortical regions that are common between CoBraD	Group comparison of the different CoBraD versus healthy controls. Compute map-extend similarity	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No

Structural patterns differences between socio-economical groups within CoBraDs	Several CoBraD structural pattern differences, compared to healthy controls, will differ accounting by socio-economical group differences	Voxel/vertex-wise Group comparison within each CoBraD, between different socio-economic groups	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Develop specific atlases for open science use	Atlases for CoBraD will allow to identify common structural, WM/DTI, rsfMRI patterns within and across CoBraD	Compute z-score for individual participants compared to same CoBraD group and versus Healthy controls. Individual reports based on normalized data (w-score / z-score)	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Develop data augmentation schemes to improve ML/DL outcomes	MRI-specific data augmentation schemes will increase the prediction performance of AI outcomes in the platform	Define set of translation/rotation realistic rules. Use GAN models to generate realistic MRI data for training	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
Asses neurodegenerative structural brain changes in older adults with new onset seizures or sleep disorders	AD signature similarity (%) will be higher in such individuals than without COBRAD	logistic regression, CTh measure. Signature neurodegeneration (Dickerson etal 2009)	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No
prediction of CoBrad Co-morbidity (cross sectional data) from single RWD - imaging	MRI-data alone can predict cobrad co-morbidity with high accuracy (>70%)	ANOVA, LDA/SVM	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	No

2.2.2 BIOFLUIDS WORK GROUP (WG-BF)

Table 5 Biofluids work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
To investigate the main differences and similarities in neurological biomarkers among CoBraD	CoBraDs share pathological mechanisms and therefore biomarkers, thus reliably identification of these disease requires a screening for several biomarkers.	Analysis of several biomarkers (eg neurofilaments, amyloid protein (Ab40 & 42), Tau, pTau231, GFAP, insulin, cortisol, and others*) via SIMOA, O-LINK and	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

		ELISA techniques, cortisol, and others ²) via SIMOA, PEA and ELISA techniques.				
To investigate the relationship between Alzheimer or Parkinson symptoms (motor and cognitive) and central or peripheral insulin levels.	Alzheimer or Parkinson Disease progression is positively correlated with insulin level/resistance.	Correlation analysis (symptoms vs insulin levels) or predictive models (Insulin levels predicting PD or AZ stages, controlled by the presence of risk genes (eg APOe3);	not feasible because absence of DNA evaluation, but chronotype (rMEQ) and Sleep/CRAR can be used instead as covariants of those predictive models.		Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A Yes
Investigate how biomarkers of metabolism may affect other neurodegenerative markers	Higher catabolic markers will be negatively associated with markers of neurodegeneration	Assess if cortisol/insulin levels account for differences in tau, nfl etc levels after accounting for disease severity (?atrophy, ?MMSE?)	Valid		Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A No

2.3 SCIENCE OF SCIENCE WORK GROUPS

2.3.1 MACHINE LEARNING AND EXPERT SYSTEMS WORK GROUP (WG-ML)

Table 6 Machine learning and expert systems work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Assess ES's usefulness for Diagnosis of CoBraD	The ES will optimize the diagnostic process with regard to time, cost, and outcomes	We will use a variety of models (e.g., PUC4's model and the gold standards) to implement them in ES. We will use these models to	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A

² A full description of the proteomic variables that can be measured from MES-CoBraD participants' biological samples is annexed (i.e., ANNEX VI) to deliverable D3.2 – Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation.

	The diagnosis for a given patient will affect their unique case outcomes	test the ES's hypotheses. The ES will provide metrics to check the significance and the specificity of the Diagnosis and the Treatment.	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
	The ES will provide more accurate and comprehensive diagnosis	The knowledge base that will be implemented will be updated with the gold standards and our hypotheses outcome and will assist the ES in making decisions.	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
	The ES will allow for more cost-effective treatment decisions		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
Assess ES's usefulness for Treatment of CoBraD	The ES will increase the chance of implementing evidence-based treatment options		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A
	The ES will increase the chance of better outcomes		Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	N/A

2.3.2 AUTOMATIC QUALITY CONTROL WORK GROUP (WG-AUTOQC)

Table 7 Automatic quality control work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Understand how to properly anonymize the input data	Proper anonymization requires the understanding of individual variable semantics and their metadata and depersonalization prior to uploading into cloud repositories	Obtain feedback from clinician-scientists (users) who understand the semantics of data in developing an ontology of variables. Identify clusters of features of these variables for identifying proper anonymization approaches. Anonymization and/or pseudo-anonymization through a tool deployed	Valid	N/A	N/A	Yes

directly within the Local Area
Network of the clinics

Define a common internal data model for the MES-CoBraD components	Harmonization of data into a model will require understanding of the semantic information these structures carry, and how they are best exploited for analyses. Multiple solutions may exist	Each of the possible data-sources is analyzed and a common data model shared among the MES-CoBraD components (possibly standard and well known to the scientific community) will be used.	Valid	N/A	N/A	No
Improve the AI model accuracy	The data cleaning and harmonization will allow to train more accurate AI models.	Train models both on raw and clean data and compare the resulting model accuracy.	Valid / Obsolete	N/A	N/A	No

2.3.3 USER INTERFACE WORK GROUP (WG-UX)

Table 8 User interface work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
To assess the impact of user experience variables on users' intentions of future use of the MES-CoBraD System	Based on UX, Usability and Technology Acceptance/Adoption literature we will identify some most likely variables determinants of user's intentions of future use of the system.	Statistical methods to be employed are Regression Analysis, Path Analysis or Structural Equation Modeling.	Valid	N/A	N/A	No
To find out the determinants of main user experience variables	Based on a literature review of UX, Usability and Technology Acceptance/Adoption we will identify most likely determinants of UX variables.	Statistical methods to be employed are Regression Analysis, Path Analysis or Structural Equation Modeling.	Valid	N/A	N/A	No

Evaluating menu placement within the Platform UI	Left side navigation with drop down menu offers the user quick access to sections and a good view of the information on the screen.	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluation of the colors used in UI design - harmonization and integration in the project specific color palette	Using shades of blue, specific to the MES-CoBraD project, results in a good visual impact for the user	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluating good names for main menu sections within the Platform UI	The sections of the main menu of the platform are named correctly and suggestively for the user	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluating the usefulness of a search button in the UI	The existence of a search button in the UI facilitates finding data and information, using keywords.	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Learnability assessment (the ease with which the use of the UI platform is learned, so that users can quickly perform the proposed tasks)	Using user-centred semantic harmonization will facilitate the learning process of using the MES-CoBraD Platform	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire - users's ratings of the ease and time to learn the system	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluation of Effectiveness (utility for supporting intended tasks)	The use of the platform ensures a successful performance of the intended tasks	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire - users's ratings of the system's ability to promote their performance and productivity	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluation of the frequency of errors (frequency, severity of errors and easy recovery)	Access and use of the platform is done without or with few errors.	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire - user's rating of the errors impact on using system and their	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

		ability to recover from errors				
Evaluate Iconic Visual metaphor in Platform UI	Iconic Visual metaphor in Platform UI can simplify the user understanding of the functionalities offered by the MES-CoBraD Platform	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes
Evaluate User Satisfaction	The use of the MES-CoBraD platform provides satisfaction to users.	Testing and evaluation by questionnaire - user's rating of their fondness, perceptions and opinions of the system and its features	Valid	Pending data integration; Pending results	N/A	Yes

2.4 SOCIOECONOMIC WORK GROUPS

2.4.1 ETHICS, POLICY, SOCIETY WORK GROUP (WG-POLICY)

Table 9 Ethics, policy, society work group information

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods	Re-evaluation of hypothesis/analyses	Results	Recommendations based on results	Active Leader
Examine pathways to diagnosis within the MES-CoBraD platform accounting for SES and health systems.	H0: No differences in pathways to diagnosis across groups H1: Time to diagnosis will be longer for those with lower SES, and in rural areas	Patient questionnaires within platform.	Valid	Development of analytical plan, next steps	N/A	Yes
Examine pathways to diagnosis within the MES-CoBraD platform accounting for SES and health systems.	H0: No differences observed across health systems H1: Differences in time to diagnosis, healthcare utilization leading up to diagnosis will differ across	Patient questionnaires within platform.	valid	Development of analytical plan, next steps	N/A	Yes

health system types (UK, Spain, Greece, Israel).

Examine how use of the MES-CoBraD Platform affects the patient/doctor relationship	<p>H0: there is no appreciable difference in the relationship healthcare professional/patient when the AI is introduced</p> <p>H1: There is a difference, but it is not perceived by either patient or clinician</p> <p>H2: There is a difference, and it is perceived by one or both patient and/or clinician</p>	<p>Dedicated focus groups with patients and with clinicians, desktop analysis, questionnaires, analysis of the UATs</p> <p>Assess (a) clinician feeling of empowerment, (b) patient experience of depersonalization in the doctor/patient relationship. If present, identify activities and strategies that are protective as covariates</p>	valid	N/A	N/A	Yes
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3 PUBLICATION & PRESENTATION REFERENCES

Table 10 Publication and presentation references information

Title	Conference/Journal	Location (if relevant)	Link (if available)	Comments	Authors	Partners Involved
Intelligent Querying for Implementing Building Aggregation Pipelines	IISA 2022	Corfu, Greece		This paper describes the work carried out for the Query builder	Alexakis K, Kapsalis P, Mylona Z, Korpakakis G, Karakolis E, Ntanos C, Askounis D	NTUA
Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia: A Controlled Trial on Sleep and Memory Outcomes	ESRS 2022	Athens, Greece		CBTi is helpful in improving insomnia in people with MCI. Whether it helps in delaying cognitive decline requires longer follow up.	Sykara K, Martin-Ramirez J, Mougias M, Tsekou H, Krithinaki F, Andronas N, Karageorgiou KE, Karageorgiou E for the MES-CoBraD Study Group	NIA
Cortical microstructure in primary progressive aphasia: a multicenter study	Alzheimer Res Ther	Journal	https://alzres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13195-022-00974-0		Ilán-Gala I, Montal V, Borrego-Écija S, Mandelli ML, Falgàs N, Welch AE, Pegueroles J, Santos-Santos M, Bejanin A, Alcolea D, Dols-Icardo O, Belbin O, Sánchez-Saudinós MB, Bargalló N, González-Ortiz S, Lladó A, Blesa R, Dickerson BC, Rosen HJ, Miller BL, Lleó A, Gorno-Tempini ML, Sánchez-Valle R, Fordea J	SP
Missing Value Imputation Methods for Electronic Health Records	IEEE Access 2023	Online	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10057378		Konstantinos Psychogyios, Loukas Ilias, Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Askounis	NTUA
Impact of Sleep on Population Health & Outcomes.	Workshop on Sleep Health. Sussex Integrated Care Board, Sussex, UK. March 7 th 2023	online	Internal recording for the SICB UK	Education of current impact of sleep disorders as a CoBraD, and the solution provided through MES-CoBraD	Elissaios Karageorgiou, Emily Adrion	NIA, UE
Sleep and Neurocognitive Disorders – Non-pharmacologic Therapies.	12th Panhellenic Conference “Neurology Days,” Kalambaka, Greece. November 5 th , 2022	In-person and online	https://youtu.be/ojBCiOlz9fE?t=1952	Within a larger presentation on Sleep and NCD interactions within CoBraD, including NIA findings supported by MES-CoBraD	Elissaios Karageorgiou	NIA

D4.5

Scientific Aims, Testable Hypotheses and Scientifically Sound, Evidence-based Recommendations for the Assessment and Management of CoBraD in real-world practice – v4

Sleep-mediated cognitive assessment and sleep architecture associations for real-world diagnostic phenotyping of neurocognitive disorders	AAIC 2023	In person and online	Sleep-mediated (and point) cognitive abilities (esp. episodic memory) are affected by shorter sleep times. Sleep-mediated spontaneous recall effects are dependent on the integrity of REM sleep. Since circadian and ultradian acetylcholine rhythms peak during wakefulness and REM sleep, it is possible that both late evening cognition and sleep-mediated memory reflects a person's cholinergic capacity, as represented in subsequent REM sleep.	Elissaios Karageorgiou, MD PhD, Konstantina Sykara, BSc MA, Nikolaos Andronas, MD, Athanasia Alexoudi, MD PhD, Zoe Devenopoulou, Julie Pitman, RPSGT, and Klimentini E Karageorgiou, MD PhD	NIA
Potential predictive value of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation before chronic cortical stimulation for epilepsy partialis continua	Brain Stimulation	Potential predictive value of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation before chronic cortical stimulation for epilepsy partialis continua - Brain Stimulation: Basic, Translational, and Clinical Research in Neuromodulation (brainstimjrn.com)	A. Rhys Potter, F. Hallal-Peche, I. Stavropoulos, L. Price, D. Jimenez-Jimenez, S. Freigang, R. Selway, I. Rosenzweig, M. Lazaro, G. Alarcon, A. Valentin	KCL	
Mes-CoBraD: an open-source research platform for integrated data collection and analysis	9th Congress of European Acedemy of Neurology	Budapest; in person and online	Ioannis Stavropoulos, Elissaios Karageorgiou, Christos Ntanos, George Doukas, Ophir Keret, Antonino Sirchia, Juan Fortea, Sandra Gimenez Badia, Jonathan Cedernaes, Luiz Eduardo Mateus Brandao, Iacob Cracianu, Emily Adrion, Vassilis Stamoulos, , Sergi Vasquez Maymir, Antonio Valentin	KCL	
Mes-CoBraD: an open-source research platform for integrated epilepsy-EEG data collection and analysis	35th International Epilepsy Congress	Dublin; in person and online	I Stavropoulos, M Kontoulis, L Ilias, G Doukas, E Nianiou, M Pina, M Dolzan, F Benninger, S Gimenez Badia, A Glik, I Goldberg, E Karageorgiou, C Ntanos, O Keret, A Valentin	KCL	
Let the AI assisted medicine remain human - Developing a care centered model of ethical decision making in AI based healthcare	3rd CINI National Lab AIIS Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Ital IA 2023) - Thematic Workshop: Responsible and Trustworthy AI	Pisa, in person	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3486/	Francesca Morpurgo, Carmela Occhipinti	CEL

Basal forebrain atrophy along the Alzheimer's disease continuum in adults with Down syndrome	Alzheimer's & Dementia	Journal	DOI: 10.1002/alz.12999	"Mateus Rozalem Aranha, Maria Florencia Iulita, Victor Montal, Jordi Pegueroles, Alexandre Bejanin, Lídia Vaqué-Alcázar, Michel J. Grothe, Maria Carmona-Iragui, Laura Videla, Bessy Benejam, Javier Arranz1 Concepción Padilla, Sílvia Valldeneu, Isabel Barroeta, Miren Altuna, Susana Fernández, Laia Ribas, Natalia Valle-Tamayo, Daniel Alcolea, Sofia González-Ortiz, Núria Bargalló, Henrik Zetterberg, Kaj Blennow, Rafael Blesa, Thomas Wisniewski, Jorge Busciglio, A. Claudio Cuello, Alberto Lleó, Juan Fortea	SP
Cross-sectional versus longitudinal cognitive assessments for the diagnosis of symptomatic Alzheimer's disease in adults with Down syndrome	Alzheimer's & Dementia	Journal	DOI: 10.1002/alz.13073	"Laura Videla, Bessy Benejam, María Carmona-Iragui, Isabel Barroeta, Susana Fernández, Javier Arranz, Sumia Elbachiri Azzahchi, Miren Altuna, Concepción Padilla, Sílvia Valldeneu, Jordi Pegueroles, Víctor Montal, Mateus Rozalem Aranha, Lídia Vaqué-Alcázar Maria Florencia Iulita Daniel Alcolea Alexandre Bejanin Sebastià Videla Rafael Blesa Alberto Lleó, Juan Fortea	SP
Plasma glial fibrillary acidic protein and neurofilament light chain for the diagnostic and prognostic evaluation of frontotemporal dementia	Translational Neurodegeneration	Journal	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40035-021-00275-w	Nuole Zhu, Miguel Santos-Santos, Ignacio Illán-Gala, Victor Montal, Teresa Estellés, Isabel Barroeta, Miren Altuna, Javier Arranz, Laia Muñoz, Olivia Belbin, Isabel Sala, Maria Belén Sánchez-Saudinós, Andrea Subirana, Laura Videla, Jordi Pegueroles, Rafael Blesa, Jordi Clarimón, Maria Carmona-Iragui, Juan Fortea, Alberto Lleó, and Daniel Alcolea	SP

